

RESEARCH ARTICLE OPEN ACCESS

Farmers' Preferences for Sustainable Crop Protection: An Integrated Choice and Latent Variable Approach

Philip K. Miriti^{1,2} | Stefan Sieber^{1,3} | Xiaohua Yu²

¹Farm Economics and Ecosystem Services, Leibniz Centre for Agricultural Landscape Research (ZALF), Müncheberg, Germany | ²Department of Agricultural Economics and Rural Development, Georg-August-Universität Göttingen, Göttingen, Germany | ³Department of Agricultural Economics, Faculty of Life Sciences, Humboldt University of Berlin, Berlin, Germany

Correspondence: Philip K. Miriti (philipkiriinya.miriti@zalf.de)

Received: 10 November 2025 | **Revised:** 9 February 2026 | **Accepted:** 5 March 2026

Keywords: farmer preferences | integrated pest management | social-psychological factors | sustainable crop protection

ABSTRACT

This study analyzes farmers' preferences for sustainable crop protection, focusing on Integrated Pest Management (IPM) practices by incorporating social-psychological factors to capture economic and behavioral dimensions. Using data from German and Polish potato farmers, we apply an integrated choice and latent variable framework that combines a discrete choice experiment with structural equation modeling. Results reveal substantial heterogeneity in preferences across and within countries. Polish farmers comprise economically driven segments prioritizing farm income and yield stability alongside an environmentally oriented group with high self-efficacy. While German farmers predominantly emphasize economic outcomes, they significantly value advisory support and substantial pesticide residue reduction. Farmer preferences reflect an interaction between economic and environmental trade-offs, perceived farmer capabilities, and social influence. Findings suggest that policy interventions should align environmental objectives with farmers' economic concerns and tailor advisory support to heterogeneous farmer preferences and behavioral orientations to accelerate holistic uptake of sustainable crop protection practices.

1 | Introduction

The global agricultural sector faces increasing pressure to balance food security with the need to minimize negative environmental impacts (Springmann et al. 2018; Nagesh et al. 2023). A critical challenge in this pursuit is reducing pesticide use, which is increasingly linked to adverse effects on human health and biodiversity. Despite stricter regulations, pesticides¹ use continues to rise globally, driven mainly by the intensification of agriculture. For example, the global pesticide use intensity surpasses agricultural output growth nearly two-fold, while herbicide use is increasing at twice the rate of population growth (Hedlund et al. 2020; Wyckhuys et al. 2022).

Within the European Union (EU), potato production is particularly pesticide-intensive due to the crop's high susceptibility to pests and diseases (Morugán-Coronado et al. 2024; Tourinho

et al. 2025). As a result, protection practices largely rely on insecticides, fungicides, and post-harvest treatments. To address the environmental pressures associated with intensive pesticide use, sustainable approaches such as Integrated Pest Management (IPM) have emerged as a promising alternative, which involves promoting ecologically based pest control strategies while reducing reliance on chemical inputs (Finger et al. 2024). Despite its potential benefits, holistic adoption of IPM practices by farmers remains inconsistent and often falls short of policy objectives, including the EU's Farm to Fork strategy targets (Deguine et al. 2021; Schneider et al. 2023).

Understanding factors that influence farmers' decision-making processes is crucial for promoting the widespread adoption of IPM practices (Deguine et al. 2021; Sánchez Bogado et al. 2024). Existing research has mainly focused on technical knowledge, economic factors, and policy and

This is an open access article under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/) License, which permits use, distribution and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

© 2026 The Author(s). *Sustainable Development* published by ERP Environment and John Wiley & Sons Ltd.

regulatory measures as key drivers, see (Möhring and Finger 2022; Gensch et al. 2024; Larki Bolfarici et al. 2024; Trèves et al. 2025). However, growing evidence suggests that these factors alone are insufficient to explain adoption behavior, as farmers' decisions are also shaped by behavioral and social-psychological dimensions (Chèze et al. 2020; Tran et al. 2023; Wuepper et al. 2023; Miriti and Lambarra-Lehnhardt 2025). Therefore, adoption decisions reflect complex interactions among economic and environmental considerations, regulatory measures, and behavioral motivations (Kaiser et al. 2024).

Reflecting on this complexity, farmer behavior in adopting sustainable agricultural practices has been explored through various conceptual frameworks. Economic approaches typically emphasize rational choice and profit maximization, focusing on economic outcomes such as yields, costs, and risks (Feder et al. 1985; McFadden 1973). Complementing this perspective, behavioral frameworks such as the Theory of Planned Behavior highlight the role of attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control in shaping adoption decisions (Ajzen 1991; Beedell and Rehman 2000). Other strands of the literature draw on innovation diffusion theory, emphasizing learning processes and the perceived compatibility and complexity of new practices (Rogers 2003; Pannell et al. 2006). Building on these insights, integrated approaches combine economic and behavioral perspectives to capture both observable trade-offs and latent behavioral factors influencing farmer choices (Ben-Akiva et al. 2002; Walker and Ben-Akiva 2002).

Consistent with this literature, studies using stated preference methods have consistently shown the existence of preference heterogeneity among farmers (Broch and Vedel 2012; Doherty et al. 2021; Zemo and Termansen 2022; Schulze et al. 2024). While heterogeneity has mainly been attributed to differences in the socioeconomic characteristics of farmers (Hess and Rose 2012), such factors often overlook the social-psychological processes and contextual drivers that underpin decision-making. Consequently, incorporating social-psychological variables in choice modeling offers a more robust approach for explaining heterogeneity (Daly et al. 2012; Kim et al. 2014). Against this background, we conduct a cross-country farm-level analysis of preferences for adopting IPM practices among Polish and German potato farmers and explicitly incorporate social-psychological factors, namely instrumental values, self-efficacy, and social norms, into the choice framework. We employ the integrated choice and latent variable (ICLV) model proposed by Ben-Akiva et al. (2002), which combines stated discrete choice models (DCM) with structural equation models (SEM) to incorporate social-psychological factors. Drawing from Boxall and Adamowicz (2002), we integrate SEM and a hybrid latent class logit (LCL) model to capture the observed and unobserved heterogeneity among farmers by accounting for the underlying social-psychological factors (Kim et al. 2014).

While the ICLV approach has been used in environmental and agricultural economics to study issues such as conservation policies, pro-environmental behavior, animal health programs, and agri-environmental scheme participation

(Lundhede et al. 2015; Czajkowski et al. 2017; Sok et al. 2018; Chang et al. 2024), its application to sustainable crop protection decisions in countries such as Germany and Poland is underexplored. By integrating behavioral aspects into the choice framework, this study contributes to the growing body of behavioral research in three ways. First, it provides a cross-country ICLV application to sustainable crop protection decisions in potato systems, comparing Germany and Poland. Second, it explicitly links social-psychological constructs to both utility formation and preference segmentation using a combined ICLV latent class framework. Third, it demonstrates how heterogeneous latent profiles translate into distinct IPM uptake patterns, offering actionable insights for differentiated policy design.

The remaining sections of the paper are structured as follows: Section 2 provides an overview of the conceptual framework and the theoretical background of the study, and indicators for social-psychological constructs. Section 3 outlines the methodology, including the survey design and data, the DCE and econometrics models. Section 4 presents empirical results, followed by a discussion in Section 5. Section 6 presents the conclusions; Section 7 presents the policy recommendations and Section 8 highlights the limitations and areas for future research.

2 | Conceptual Framework

2.1 | The ICLV Conceptual Framework

To develop our conceptual framework for farmer preferences for sustainable crop protection using the ICLV approach, we adopt a pluralistic perspective that integrates insights from behavioral theories. This is in line with Kreft et al. (2021) who combined concepts from multiple theories to explain farmers' adoption behavior of climate change mitigation measures. In our study, the framework emphasizes three social-psychological constructs relevant for our study, namely, social norms from the theory of planned behavior (Ajzen 1991), self-efficacy from the social-cognitive theory (Bandura 1991), and instrumental value from farmers' value orientations (Gasson 1973). In addition, we draw from a wide range of literature on behavioral factors influencing the adoption of sustainable agricultural practices (Sok et al. 2018; Barghusen et al. 2021; Le Coent et al. 2021; Kreft et al. 2021; Knapp et al. 2021; Sarma 2022; Graskemper et al. 2022; Li et al. 2023; Miriti et al. 2023; Regassa et al. 2023; Chang et al. 2024; Meunier et al. 2024; Erekaló et al. 2025).

Self-efficacy refers to a person's belief in their own capability to successfully perform a specific task within a given domain (Bandura 1991). Individuals with high perceived self-efficacy tend to view challenges as manageable, whereas those with low perceived self-efficacy are more likely to perceive them as insurmountable barriers (Newman et al. 2019). In agricultural contexts, farmers with high perceived efficacy are likely to adopt and implement new sustainable agricultural practices such as IPM, while those with lower self-efficacy may avoid such changes due to perceived complexity or risk (Han and Niles 2023).

Social norms represent perceived social pressure and reference group confirmation that are likely to influence an

individual's intention to implement a given task (Ajzen 1991; Hüttel et al. 2022). Social norms can motivate farmers to conform to socially accepted practices to maintain social status, gain approval, or avoid disapproval within their community. Consequently, social norms can encourage the adoption of sustainable practices when such practices are widely accepted, but may also act as barriers when conventional farming practices remain dominant (Le Coent et al. 2021). Further, Erekaló et al. (2025) and Meunier et al. (2024) highlight the role of social norms in shaping the adoption of sustainable agricultural practices. Instrumental values refer to where farming is viewed as a means of obtaining income and security with pleasant working conditions (Gasson 1973). Farmers' instrumental values influence farmers' behavior toward adopting sustainable agricultural practices. Farmers guided by strong instrumental values tend to evaluate practices in terms of their capacity to safeguard yields, reduce risks, and stabilize income. Sustainable practices that align with these values, such as IPM strategies that improve efficiency or reduce losses, are more likely to be adopted. In contrast, those perceived as potentially undermining income or working conditions are less likely to be adopted (Leduc et al. 2023).

Against this theoretical and empirical background, we assume that farmers' decision-making with respect to the adoption of sustainable crop protection practices like IPM is determined by farm structural factors and farmers' individual characteristics, including behavioral factors. Particularly, our study emphasizes three social-psychological constructs, which are self-efficacy, social norms, and instrumental values. The ICLV framework provides a suitable approach for incorporating such social-psychological constructs into the analysis of farmer preferences using DCE (Ben-Akiva et al. 2002). Subsequently, we integrate these three constructs into our model to complement the analysis of farmers' choice behavior, as illustrated in Figure 1.

2.2 | Indicators for Social-Psychological Constructs

Farmers' self-efficacy was measured using an 11-point Likert scale with constructs adopted from Knapp et al. (2021) and Bandura (2006). We asked farmers to indicate the extent to which they can find solutions if there is a problem with potato production, the extent to which they can solve crop protection problems and how confident they are in reducing pesticide use and produce potatoes successfully. For instrumental values, we also used an 11-point Likert scale to assess how important it is for farmers to achieve high potato yields, obtain high income from potato production including direct payments and reduction of workload related to potato production based on Gasson (1973) framework on value orientations and lastly, we measured farmers' social norms in regards to adopting IPM using a 6-point Likert scale with questions adopted from Despotović et al. (2019) and Tama et al. (2021). We included both injunctive norms, which refer to the expected or perceived (dis)approval by others, and a descriptive norm, which refers to perceptions of what others are actually doing (Cialdini et al. 1990). Farmers were asked the extent to which their decisions could be influenced by neighbors, influential people and other farmers. Table 1 summarizes social-psychological constructs.

3 | Methods

3.1 | Survey Design and Data

The study surveyed² potato farmers from Poland and Germany between March and November 2024 through an online survey administered through LimeSurvey. Participation invitations were distributed via email, and before accessing the questionnaire, participants were presented with an informed consent form outlining the purpose and scope of the study. The

FIGURE 1 | Conceptual framework of the ICLV model used in this study. Adapted and modified from Kim et al. (2014) and Sok et al. (2018).

TABLE 1 | Description of variables of interest.

Variables	Question	Scale	References
Self-efficacy	If there is a problem in potato production, I usually find a solution	0–10 Likert scale	Bandura (2006) and Knapp et al. (2021)
	I can solve most problems in crop protection if I make an effort		
	I am confident that I can reduce pesticides and at the same time produce potatoes successfully		
Instrumental value	How important is achieving a high potato yield (dt/ha) for your decisions regarding crop protection?	0–10 Likert scale	Gasson (1973)
	How important is achieving a high income from potato production (including direct payments) for your decisions regarding crop protection?		
	How important is reducing the workload related to potato production for your decisions regarding crop protection?		
Social norms	Most farmers would adopt IPM practices if their neighbors adopted Integrated Pest Management practices ^a	0–5 Likert scale	Despotović et al. (2019) and Tama et al. (2021)
	I would adopt IPM practices if the people in my life whose opinion is important to me would support my decision to adopt the practices ^b		
	I would adopt IPM practices if other farmers think that I should adopt environmentally friendly approaches ^b		

Note: The questions were adapted and modified to reflect the context of potato production and sustainable crop protection.

^aDenotes the descriptive norm question while.

^bDenotes injunctive norm questions.

questionnaire was structured into two main sections. The first section gathered information on socio-demographic characteristics, farmers' adoption of IPM practices, and social-psychological constructs. The second section contained the DCE aimed at eliciting farmers' preferences and decision-making processes regarding IPM implementation.

The IPM practices included in the survey were selected in collaboration with potato IPM experts from Poland and Germany and refined through focus group discussions with local farmers. Summary statistics of the IPM practices reported by farmers by class are provided in Tables A1 and A2 in the appendix. The social-psychological constructs were measured through farmer self-reported multi-item Likert scale as highlighted in Section 2.2. In total, 172 and 180 fully completed surveys were collected from Poland and Germany, respectively.

3.2 | Discrete Choice Experiment

The DCE was conducted among potato farmers in Poland and Germany. To identify the key attributes to consider in DCE design, first, we carried out an extensive literature review on key socioeconomic attributes of IPM practices. The attributes initially identified were validated by IPM experts using the Delphi approach which sought expert opinions and views (Cole et al. 2020; Kelemen et al. 2023), and finally conducted a pre-test

to check whether the attributes and levels were plausible and understandable to farmers. The attributes identified included source of IPM advisory support, reduction of pesticide residues, time to start or transition to implementing IPM practices, farm income, and production changes in a cropping season, as shown in Table A3.

Following the identification of relevant attributes and their corresponding levels, an experimental design was generated using the statistical software JMP (SAS Institute Inc 2023). A full factorial design would have produced 162 distinct profiles ($3^4 \times 2$), resulting in 13,041 unique pairwise choice sets ($(162 \times (162-1))/2$), which would impose excessive cognitive burden on respondents (Gao et al. 2010; Scarpa et al. 2013). We used a D-optimal fractional factorial design that resulted in 24 choice sets based on the covariance matrix of a multinomial logit model that offers an efficient combination of orthogonality, level balance, and minimum overlap (Kuhfeld 2010).

The 24 choice sets were randomly divided into four blocks, each containing six choice sets (Huber and Zwerina 1996; Regassa et al. 2021). The blocks were randomly assigned to respondents using LimeSurvey's built-in randomization logic, ensuring that each participant was presented with only one block. Consequently, each farmer responded to six choice tasks. An example of a choice card is illustrated in Figure A1. For a comprehensive overview of the experimental design, including a

detailed rationale for attribute and level selection, see Miriti et al. (2025).

3.3 | The ICLV Model

The ICLV model offers an econometric framework to supplement economic theory with psychological constructs (Ben-Akiva et al. 2002). The ICLV model combines two components, a structural equation model that captures latent psychological factors and a choice model that represents observed decision-making behavior (Ben-Akiva et al. 2002). In this study, we use the ICLV approach to incorporate latent social-psychological factors, as outlined in Section 2.1, into the analysis of farmer preferences for IPM attributes. The ICLV framework can be implemented using two main approaches, namely the sequential and simultaneous approaches. In the sequential approach, a special case of SEM referred to as the multiple indicator and multiple causes (MIMIC) model is used to test the relationships between socioeconomic factors and indicators of latent constructs. The pre-constructed conditional means of the latent variables are subsequently incorporated into the choice model (Bahamonde-Birke and Ortúzar 2014). The simultaneous approach involves estimating the MIMIC model and the choice model in one step (Bahamonde-Birke et al. 2017).

While the sequential approach provides consistent estimates by incorporating the pre-constructed conditional means through a two-step procedure, the strength of this approach is that it allows prior assessment of the validity of the hypothesized constructs, enhancing the robustness and interpretability of the measurement model (Raveau et al. 2010). The single-step simultaneous approach has a complex structure, and the estimation process often suffers from convergence problems due to multiple integrals, especially when multiple latent variables and underlying indicators are included in the model, and less attention is given to the validity of the hypothesized constructs (Raveau et al. 2010; Sok et al. 2018). Notwithstanding these limitations, a simultaneous approach was initially pursued to estimate the ICLV model. However, the process proved computationally intensive and failed to converge when multiple latent variables were included. A model with a single latent variable was successfully estimated, and the results are presented in Table A4. For completeness of results, the normal mixed logit estimates are also reported in Table A5. Further, Chang et al. (2024) compared results from the sequential and the simultaneous approach and found that the parameter estimates are largely similar, suggesting that either method yields comparable substantive interpretations. Therefore, the study adopts the sequential estimation approach, in which latent variables enter the analysis in two ways: directly as explanatory variables in the utility function, and indirectly by explaining preference heterogeneity through class membership in the LCL.

In the ICVL model we focus on self-efficacy, social norms, and instrumental values because they are closely aligned with farmers' perceived ability to implement IPM, social influence within farming communities, and economic and environmental trade-offs inherent in crop protection decisions. These constructs are particularly well suited to a stated choice context, where

adoption decisions involve both perceived feasibility and value-based trade-offs. While other constructs such as risk perception, trust in institutions, and general environmental concern are also relevant in farmer behavior studies, including a larger set of latent variables would substantially increase model complexity in the ICLV framework.

3.4 | Empirical Framework

3.4.1 | Structural Equation Model

The MIMIC model in this study is implemented following the framework proposed by Bollen (1989). As a special form of SEM, the MIMIC model enables estimation of latent variables using multiple observed indicators while simultaneously incorporating explanatory variables that influence the latent constructs (Joreskog and Goldberger 1975). The model is composed of the measurement and the structural model; the structural model relates the latent constructs to a set of indicators and can be expressed as:

$$Y_{in} = \lambda_i LV_n + \epsilon_{in} \quad (1)$$

where Y_{in} are the observed indicators i for farmer n , λ_i are the factor loadings for indicator i , LV_n is the latent construct for farmer n and ϵ_{in} is the measurement error, which is assumed to be normally distributed with zero means and diagonal covariance matrices. The structural equation model incorporates a set of exogenous explanatory variables that influence the latent constructs, and it can be expressed as:

$$LV_n = \Gamma X_n + \zeta_n \quad (2)$$

where LV_n denote the latent construct for farmer n , X_n is a vector of exogenous variables, Γ is a vector of structural parameters and ζ_n is a random disturbance term. The model fit is assessed using the standard SEM goodness of fit measures including the Comparative Fit Index (CFI) and Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI), both with recommended thresholds of ≥ 0.95 ; the Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR) with a threshold of ≤ 0.08 ; and the Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA) with a threshold of ≤ 0.08 (Schermele-Engel et al. 2003; Kaiser et al. 2024; Chang et al. 2024). The MIMIC framework further enables assessment of construct validity. Convergent validity, which measures the extent to which the indicators capture the latent constructs, is assessed using the average variance extracted (AVE ≥ 0.50) and composite reliability (CR ≥ 0.70) (Fornell and Larcker 1981).

3.4.2 | The Discrete Choice Kernel

The choice model framework is based on the random utility theory (McFadden 1973). Therefore, assuming the utility maximization of a farmer, the utility that the farmer n derives from alternative n given a choice k situation is given by

$$U_{mvk} = \beta_n x_{mvk} + \epsilon_{mvk} \quad (3)$$

where x_{mvk} denotes the attributes of IPM practices, β_n is a vector that corresponds to the coefficients of the IPM attributes and ϵ_{mvk} is the error term. For an ICLV model that integrates latent variables, farmers' utility does not solely depend on the attributes of IPM practices but also on farmers'

social-psychological factors, which are modeled as latent variables since they are unobservable. The latent variables are subsequently included in Equation (3) and the utility of the farmer can be expressed as:

$$U_{nvk} = \beta_n x_{nvk} + \gamma_n z_n + \varepsilon_{nvk} \quad (4)$$

where z_n denotes a set of latent variables associated with the farmer n and γ_n is a vector of parameters linking latent variables of the farmer n in the utility function (Daly et al. 2012; Chang et al. 2024).

3.4.3 | Latent Class Logit Model

The LCL model hypothesizes that farmers can be segmented into latent classes that explain sources of preference heterogeneity for IPM practices. In this study, heterogeneity is explained using latent variables following the ICLV framework (Boxall and Adamowicz 2002). The preferences are assumed to be homogeneous within classes but heterogeneous across the different classes (Greene and Hensher 2003). The probability that a farmer n will choose alternative V given a choice scenario k given they belong to class d is represented by:

$$P(nV|d) = \prod_k \frac{\exp(\beta_d X_n V k)}{\sum_j \exp(\beta_d X_n k)} \quad (5)$$

where $X_n V k$ denotes parameters of IPM practices associated with farmer n choosing alternative V in a choice scenario k and β_d represents class-specific estimates that account for preference heterogeneity across the classes (Boxall and Adamowicz 2002). Further, LCL allows for the estimation of the probabilities for class assignment which is given by:

$$P(d) = \frac{\exp(\theta'_d z_k)}{\sum_{d=1}^D \exp(\theta'_d z_k)}, \theta'_d = 0 \quad (6)$$

where z_k represents the latent variables used to explain preference heterogeneity across the classes and θ'_d denotes parameters for specific classes, where estimates are normalized to zero to ensure the identification of parameters in other classes (Greene and Hensher 2003).

4 | Results

4.1 | Household Characteristics

Table 2 presents household characteristics of the sampled potato farmers in Poland and Germany. The average age of farmers is comparable across countries at approximately 40 years. However, the share of farmers with organized farm succession, insurance uptake, higher education levels, and organic production is more prevalent among German potato. Farmers in both countries have a comparable percentage of farmers who source crop protection information from other farmers and plant protection manufacturers. Farm size distribution differs, with the majority of Polish farmers operating smaller farms compared to

German potato farmers. However, in Germany, farmers devote a larger share of their agricultural land to potato production.

4.2 | Structural and Measurement Estimates of the MIMIC Model

Table 3 presents the estimates from the MIMIC³ model. The structural component reveals that several farm and farmer characteristics are significantly associated with the latent constructs. Age is positively associated with self-efficacy in both Poland and Germany, while its relationship with social norms and instrumental value differs across countries. Planned farm succession is positively related to all three latent constructs. Organic potato farming is negatively associated with instrumental values but positively associated with social norms and self-efficacy. Crop insurance shows positive associations with instrumental values, social norms, and self-efficacy. Information sources display heterogeneous relationships across countries, with peer farmers, farmers' organizations, and plant protection product manufacturers influencing latent constructs differently in Poland and Germany.

4.3 | Latent Class Logit Model Results

Table 4 presents findings of the LCL model results, highlighting heterogeneous preferences shaped by social-psychological constructs. The optimal number of classes that provides the best fit was assessed based on the Akaike information criterion (AIC) and the Bayesian information criterion (BIC), as shown in Table A6. A model with two classes had the lowest AIC and BIC values. Subsequently, the results are based on an LCL with two classes (Boxall and Adamowicz 2002).

In Poland, Class 1 accounts for approximately 52% of the sampled farmers. This class exhibits positive preferences for substantial reductions in pesticide residues, shorter transition periods, and both private and public advisory support. Farmers in this class are characterized by higher levels of self-efficacy and lower instrumental values. Class 2 comprises the remaining 48% of Polish farmers and displays positive preferences for IPM practices that increase farm income and minimize yield reductions, alongside negative preferences for substantial pesticide reduction. This class is associated with higher instrumental values.

In Germany, approximately 83% of farmers are predicted to belong to Class 1. Farmers in this class show strong preferences for IPM practices that increase farm income, minimize negative production effects on potato production, and prefer shorter transition periods, while being characterized by lower self-efficacy. Class 2 represents 17% of the German sample and shows positive preferences for both public and private advisory support and for substantial reductions in pesticide residues.

4.4 | Uptake of IPM Practices by Class

Table A1 presents IPM practices implemented by farmers by class. In Poland, both classes exhibited high uptake of field

TABLE 2 | Household characteristics of the sampled farmers.

Variables	Unit	Description	Poland	Germany
Age of the farmer	Number of years	Mean age of the farmers	39.72 (12.62)	40.16 (9.86)
Organic production	Percentage (%)	Percentage of farmers who produce potatoes under organic production	56.40	76.11
Succession	Percentage (%)	Percentage of farmers with organized succession	51.74	68.33
Insurance	Percentage (%)	Percentage of farmers with crop insurance	28.49	35.56
Higher education	Percentage (%)	Percentage of farmers with higher education	22.09	30.00
Sex of the farmer	Percentage (%)	Percentage of male farmers	67.72	72.33
Crop protection information from	Percentage (%)	Percentage source of crop protection information		
Other farmers			45.93	43.33
Farmers' organization			29.65	40.55
Plant protection product manufacturers			45.34	50.55
Total agricultural land of the farm (%)	Percentage (%) size category	Distribution of total farmland by size category (%)		
< 25 ha			60.47	11.67
26–50 ha			15.70	21.67
51–75 ha			5.81	20.56
> 76 ha			18.02	46.11
Share of land under potato production (%)	Percentage (%) land share	Share of land devoted to potato production (%)		
0%–25%			42.44	18.89
26%–50%			32.56	21.67
51%–75%			19.77	35.56
76%–100%			5.23	23.89

Note: Standard deviations are reported in parentheses.

hygiene practices, 70% and 68% in Classes 1 and 2, respectively, underscoring their importance as a core element of IPM. Class 2 farmers, however, reported higher adoption of efficiency-oriented practices such as adjustment of seed density, adjustment of sowing time, site-specific crop rotation, and low-to-medium mechanical weed control and use of forecasting and warning systems for pests and diseases. By contrast, Class 1 farmers showed relatively greater uptake of sprouted seed potatoes and beneficial organisms.

Table A2 reports uptake patterns among German farmers. Field hygiene practices show the highest uptake across both Class 1 (72%) and Class 2 (77%). Class 2 farmers report higher adoption of ecological and monitoring-oriented practices, including green manuring, promotion of ecological habitats, use of resistant

varieties, and regular pest and weed monitoring. Class 1 farmers show higher uptake of sowing adjustments and the use of forecasting and warning systems.

5 | Discussion

The results reveal pronounced heterogeneity in farmer preferences for IPM practices across both Poland and Germany, shaped by economic, environmental considerations and social-psychological factors. In Poland, farmers exhibit positive preferences for IPM practices that substantially reduce pesticide residues in the environment, which suggests their commitment to sustainability and environmental benefits (Kaiser et al. 2024). The presence of a large pro-environmental segment (Class 1)

TABLE 3 | Estimation results from the MIMIC model.

Structural model	Instrumental value		Social norms		Self-efficacy	
	Poland	Germany	Poland	Germany	Poland	Germany
Variables	Coefficient	Coefficient	Coefficient	Coefficient	Coefficient	Coefficient
Age of the farmer	0.104*** (0.024)	-0.119*** (0.024)	-0.053** (0.025)	0.088*** (0.029)	0.152*** (0.023)	0.195*** (0.020)
Higher education	0.002 (0.024)	0.038 (0.024)	-0.019 (0.026)	-0.045* (0.027)	-0.010 (0.024)	-0.021 (0.019)
Planned farm succession	0.137*** (0.027)	0.022 (0.026)	0.110*** (0.028)	0.097*** (0.030)	0.257*** (0.026)	0.188*** (0.022)
Organic production	-0.281*** (0.025)	-0.119*** (0.026)	0.078*** (0.027)	0.558*** (0.027)	0.123*** (0.025)	0.454*** (0.019)
Insurance	0.071*** (0.027)	0.152*** (0.024)	0.043 (0.028)	0.138*** (0.028)	0.059** (0.026)	0.102*** (0.020)
Crop protection information from						
Other farmers	0.163*** (0.025)	0.209*** (0.024)	0.056*** (0.026)	-0.084*** (0.028)	0.152*** (0.024)	0.027 (0.020)
Farmers' organization	-0.156*** (0.024)	0.043* (0.024)	-0.175*** (0.025)	-0.018 (0.028)	-0.080*** (0.024)	0.001 (0.022)
Plant protection product manufacturers	0.031 (0.024)	0.152*** (0.024)	-0.096*** (0.026)	0.126*** (0.027)	-0.019 (0.024)	0.019 (0.019)
Measurement						
[...] is reducing the workload related [...]	0.706*** (0.014)	0.652*** (0.017)				
[...] achieving a high potato yield [...]	0.858*** (0.013)	0.796*** (0.016)				
[...] achieving a high income [...]	0.722*** (0.015)	0.676*** (0.017)				
[...] if their neighbors adopted [...]			0.712*** (0.016)	0.434*** (0.025)		
[...] whose opinion is important to me [...]			0.757*** (0.016)	0.538*** (0.024)		
[...] if other farmers think that [...]			0.714*** (0.016)	0.524*** (0.024)		
[...] problem in potato production, I usually find a solution [...]					0.734*** (0.017)	0.382*** (0.024)
[...] solve most problems in crop protection [...]					0.928*** (0.017)	0.348*** (0.025)

(Continues)

TABLE 3 | (Continued)

Structural model	Instrumental value		Social norms		Self-efficacy	
	Poland	Germany	Poland	Germany	Poland	Germany
Variables	Coefficient	Coefficient	Coefficient	Coefficient	Coefficient	Coefficient
[...] reduce pesticides and at the same time produce [...]					0.483*** (0.019)	0.940*** (0.028)
RMSEA	0.056	0.018	0.023	0.040	0.069	0.020
CFI	0.994	0.998	0.999	0.981	0.954	0.998
TLI	0.990	0.998	0.998	0.972	0.973	0.998
SRMR	0.034	0.016	0.018	0.025	0.030	0.017
CR	0.880	0.657	0.882	0.767	0.882	0.658
AVE	0.588	0.491	0.528	0.524	0.554	0.493

Note: The table presents the structural and measurement estimates of the MIMIC model. Measures of model fit are reported, including RMSEA Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA), Comparative Fit Index (CFI), Tucker–Lewis Index (TLI), and Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR). Composite Reliability (CR) and Average Variance Extracted (AVE) are provided for each latent construct. Standard errors are shown in parentheses. *, **, and *** denote statistical significance at the 10%, 5% levels, and 1%, respectively.

highlights the importance of self-efficacy and non-instrumental motivations in supporting the adoption of sustainable crop protection practices. Farmers with higher self-efficacy exhibit stronger preferences for shorter transition periods, consistent with evidence that perceived capability facilitates uptake of environmentally friendly practices (Han and Niles 2023). Farmers in this class have a stronger preference for private advisory support compared to public advisory support, indicating a preference for personalized guidance. Conversely, the economically oriented Polish farmer segment (Class 2) prioritizes income gains and yield stability while exhibiting a negative preference for substantial pesticide residue reduction. This pattern aligns with prior findings showing that farmers driven by instrumental motivations tend to adopt a more entrepreneurial and production-focused management strategy (Duesberg et al. 2013; Agbenyo et al. 2025).

In Germany, the dominance of an economically oriented (Class 1) reflects the strong role of farm income and production risk management in shaping adoption decisions. Interestingly, this group is characterized by low self-efficacy but with a positive and significant preference for a shorter transition period. This combination does not imply contradiction but reflects a context in which strong advisory systems, regulatory pressure, and standardized IPM protocols reduce perceived implementation autonomy while simultaneously accelerating expected adoption timelines. Similar dynamics have been observed in contexts where external pressures, market conditions, or advisory systems encourage adoption despite psychological barriers (Dessart et al. 2019; Liu and Liu 2024; Byfuglien et al. 2025). The relatively smaller segment (Class 2) exhibits pro-environmental preferences by valuing substantial pesticide residue reduction and advisory support, highlighting the continued relevance of institutional and informational support for environmentally motivated farmers. Similar findings are reported by Ahmad (2025), who highlights the role of information and communication in

the adoption of agricultural technologies such as sustainable pest management. Across both countries, the results emphasize that advisory systems play a critical role, but their effectiveness depends on alignment with farmers' underlying motivations and perceived efficacy.

In addition, the uptake patterns of IPM practices across classes illustrate how farmer preferences and social-psychological characteristics may influence adoption decisions. Across both Poland and Germany, field hygiene shows consistently high adoption, confirming its role as a core and widely accepted component of IPM due to its low implementation costs and immediate agronomic benefits (Deguine et al. 2021). In Poland, farmers in the economically oriented class show higher uptake of efficiency-enhancing and decision-support practices such as sowing adjustments, mechanical weed control, and forecasting systems, reflecting their focus on yield stability and risk management. In contrast, the environmentally oriented class exhibits relatively higher adoption of biologically based measures, including beneficial organisms and sprouted seed potatoes, consistent with evidence that pro-environmental farmers are more willing to adopt knowledge-intensive and ecologically focused IPM practices (Dessart et al. 2019; Chèze et al. 2020).

In Germany, class-specific uptake patterns further reflect differences in institutional context and advisory systems. Farmers in the environmentally oriented class demonstrate greater adoption of ecological infrastructure, resistant varieties, and systematic pest monitoring, aligning with Germany's stronger integration of IPM principles into advisory services and agri-environmental schemes (Schneider et al. 2023). Conversely, economically oriented farmers rely more heavily on management flexibility tools such as sowing adjustments and forecasting systems, emphasizing efficiency and decision optimization.

TABLE 4 | Estimation results from LCL model.

Variables	Poland		Germany	
	Coefficient	Std. err.	Coefficient	Std. err.
Class 1				
Farm income	0.035	0.020	0.089***	0.011
IPM advisory support (reference: no support)				
Private	0.613***	0.166	-0.057	0.117
Public	0.263*	0.144	-0.010	0.099
Reduction of pesticide residues (reference: small)				
Substantial	0.328***	0.110	-0.039	0.079
Transition time to full IPM (reference: 2 years)				
4 years	0.256*	0.143	0.229**	0.099
6 years	0.157	0.185	0.110	0.112
Production losses in a cropping season (reference: production reduces by 15%)				
Production reduces by 5%	0.002	0.194	0.338***	0.109
Production reduces by 10%	0.151	0.148	0.219**	0.109
Instrumental value	-0.122**	0.055	0.250	0.286
Social norms	0.008	0.404	0.834	1.146
Self-efficacy	0.577*	0.340	-0.564*	0.313
Class share (%)	52		83	
Class 2				
Farm income	0.215***	0.036	0.098	0.105
IPM advisory support (reference: no support)				
Private	0.400	0.260	1.217***	0.471
Public	0.538**	0.210	0.807***	0.292
Reduction of pesticide residues (reference: small)				
Substantial	-0.667***	0.205	0.643**	0.274
Transition time to full IPM (reference: 2 years)				
4 years	-0.313	0.217	-0.347	0.736
6 years	-0.183	0.307	1.623	1.240
Production losses in a cropping season (reference: production reduces by 15%)				
Production reduces by 5%	1.196***	0.283	1.799	1.104
Production reduces by 10%	0.081	0.235	0.216	0.910
Class share (%)	48		17	
Constant	-0.413	0.503	1.561***	0.415
Number of respondents	172		180	
Number of observations	2064		2160	
Log-likelihood	-648.976		-677.21	

Note: To identify the model, the coefficients of the latent variables for Class 2 were normalized to zero (Greene and Hensher 2003). As a result, the estimated coefficients for Class 1 should be interpreted relative to this baseline. Therefore, they represent the inverse sign and relative magnitude of the corresponding effects in Class 2. *, **, and *** represent statistical significance at 10%, 5%, and 1% level.

6 | Conclusions

Farmer preferences play an important role in shaping decisions related to the implementation of sustainable crop protection practices such as IPM. In this study, we employed an ICLV framework that integrates SEM with DCE to incorporate social-psychological constructs into the analysis of farmer preferences. By leveraging the ICLV approach, we gain a more nuanced understanding of how social-psychological drivers shape and influence farmers' adoption preferences (Ben-Akiva et al. 2002).

Our results reveal that farmers' preferences for IPM practices are heterogeneous across classes in both Germany and Poland, with social-psychological variables providing valuable insights into these differences. In Poland, approximately 52% of the sampled farmers (Class 1) exhibit strong pro-environmental preferences, favoring IPM practices that substantially reduce pesticide residues in the environment, alongside a preference for both private and public advisory support and shorter transition times. This group is characterized by high perceived self-efficacy and low instrumental values, indicating a stronger orientation toward environmental benefits over immediate economic gains. In contrast, the remaining 48% of Polish farmers (Class 2) prefer IPM practices that are likely to increase farm income and minimize yield reductions, while exhibiting negative preferences for substantial pesticide reduction. They are characterized by high instrumental values and low self-efficacy, reflecting strong economic motivation. In Germany, farmers in Class 1 prefer IPM practices that enhance farm income, minimize negative impacts on potato production, and a four-year transition period, while also displaying low self-efficacy. Class 2 segment, however, shows a positive preference for both advisory support and substantial pesticide reduction, indicating a more pro-environment orientation.

These results highlight a key comparative insight. German farmers display a stronger instrumental orientation than Polish farmers. Several structural and contextual factors may explain this difference. First, Germany's agricultural policy and subsidy regime has historically emphasized efficiency, competitiveness, and yield stability, reinforcing instrumental motivations. Second, the advisory system in Germany is more institutionalized, with strong roles for plant protection manufacturers and farmers' associations, which often frame IPM in economic terms (Leonnig and Nielsen 2026). In contrast, advisory services in Poland are more fragmented, and peer-to-peer exchanges play a larger role, which may encourage pro-environmental orientations among some farmers. Third, social norms also matter. Polish farmers, particularly younger ones, positively associate with organic farming and peer influence, while German farmers emphasize professionalization and farming continuity as reflected by the positive association of social norms with farm succession, insurance, and plant protection product manufacturers. Together, these factors provide a plausible explanation for the observed cross-country divergence in instrumental versus environmental orientations.

7 | Policy Recommendations

The findings of this study underscore the need for differentiated interventions that explicitly account for preference heterogeneity and farmers' social-psychological factors when promoting the adoption of sustainable crop protection practices such as IPM. Policy interventions aimed at promoting widespread and holistic adoption of IPM should implement incentive structures that bundle economic and environmental benefits while accounting for heterogeneous farmer preferences and behavioral orientations. Such bundling increases the likelihood of adoption by farmers because it simultaneously addresses farm financial viability and environmental conservation goals (Luan et al. 2025).

For profit-oriented farmers, market-based instruments such as access to premium markets and sustainability labels can be linked to the adoption of IPM practices, thereby aligning economic incentives with environmental objectives such as reduced pesticide residues. This moves beyond command-and-control measures such as banning pesticides to more farmer-friendly approaches that increase the likelihood of adoption (Finger et al. 2024). On the other hand, for environmentally driven farmers, policy measures could instead focus on enabling conditions such as support for ecological infrastructure, investment in pest monitoring systems, and recognition schemes that acknowledge environmental stewardship. Such integrated incentives can strengthen both the economic and environmental rationale for IPM adoption and can help offset social-psychological factors that may hinder adoption by creating external drivers that encourage adoption regardless of farmers' initial self-efficacy or value orientation.

Strengthening advisory services is critical for enhancing IPM adoption, and policy should move beyond the traditional top-down, one-size-fits-all approach that characterizes advisory services. Pluralistic advisory systems and tailored information that reflects farmers' diverse preferences can improve uptake (Chowdhury and Kabir 2024). For example, for farmers who are economically oriented, advisory programs could emphasize the cost-saving and income-stabilizing benefits of IPM, while for environmentally oriented farmers, messages could emphasize ecological and long-term sustainability gains. Such differentiated strategies can better align advisory support with farmers' heterogeneous preferences and motivations, thereby promoting and reinforcing adoption.

8 | Limitations and Future Research

First, this study relies on a cross-sectional research design based on online survey data collected from potato farmers in Germany and Poland. While this approach is well-suited for identifying preference heterogeneity and capturing the role of social-psychological factors at a given point in time, it does not allow for the analysis of dynamic changes in farmers' behavioral responses over time. Future research could address this limitation by using panel data or longitudinal study designs to

examine how psychological factors, policy exposure, and learning processes influence IPM adoption among farmers.

Second, this study adopted a sequential integrated choice and latent variable (ICLV) approach, which allows for prior validation of latent constructs and improves the robustness of the measurement model (Raveau et al. 2010). However, in this approach, latent variables are first estimated using a structural equation model and subsequently incorporated directly into the choice model, which may lead to efficiency losses. While a fully simultaneous estimation framework could, in principle, capture the joint determination of latent variables and choices more efficiently, such models often face convergence challenges in complex settings with multiple latent variables (Raveau et al. 2010; Sok et al. 2018). Importantly, existing comparative evidence suggests that both approaches yield largely similar parameter estimates and substantive interpretations (Chang et al. 2024). Future research could nonetheless explore simultaneous ICLV estimation to further assess the robustness of behavioral insights derived from farmer preference data.

Finally, the survey was administered online, yielding 172 responses from potato farmers in Poland and 180 from Germany. While online surveys facilitate access to geographically dispersed farmers and are increasingly used in agricultural research, they may under-represent farmers who are less digitally connected or with lower digital literacy. However, the achieved sample sizes in this study are comparable to those used in stated preference and discrete choice studies in agriculture (De Salvo et al. 2018; Liu and Brouwer 2022; Bjørnåvold et al. 2022). Future studies could complement online data with mixed-mode or in-person data collection to test the stability and robustness of results across different data collection approaches.

Acknowledgments

This research was undertaken within the project SUPPORT (Supporting Uptake Integrated Pest Management and Low-Risk Pesticide Use), funded by the European Union (EU)'s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101084527, <https://he-support.eu/>. The content of this article does not reflect the official opinion of the European Union. Responsibility for the information and views expressed therein lies entirely with the authors. Open Access funding enabled and organized by Projekt DEAL.

Funding

This work was supported by HORIZON EUROPE Research and Innovation Programme, 101084527.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Endnotes

¹ Various factors influence pesticide use levels either directly or indirectly, for example pest pressure (Bebber et al. 2014; Courson et al. 2024; Mauser et al. 2025), changes in crops and agricultural practices (Hader et al. 2022), policy changes and regulation (Matousek et al. 2022; Silva et al. 2022; Kaiser 2023; Gensch et al. 2024; Finger 2024), costs and benefits of pesticide use (Oirdi et al. 2024; Rufo et al. 2024), consumer demand for healthy agricultural products (Möhring and Finger 2022; Wendt and Weinrich 2023; Oliveira et al. 2024).

² The study received ethical approval from ZALF Ethics Committee (Ref. 20231201) and ETH Zurich Ethics Commission (Ref. EK 2023-N-318).

³ The measurement model specifies the relationship between the latent variables and their corresponding observed indicators. The goodness-of-fit measures confirm that the estimated parameters meet the recommended thresholds, for example, the CFI and TLI ≥ 0.95 , SRMR ≤ 0.08 and RMSEA ≤ 0.08 (Schermelleh-Engel et al. 2003; Kaiser et al. 2024). Internal consistency reliability and convergent validity of the latent constructs were assessed using the Stata Mata function with CR values ≥ 0.50 and AVE values ≥ 0.70 . This indicates sufficient reliability and validity across all estimated latent constructs (Fornell and Larcker 1981). Further, all the parameters of the latent variables in the measurement model are statistically significant, which shows that the indicators are reliable measures of the latent constructs for both Polish and German potato farmers (Sok et al. 2018).

References

- Agbenyo, W., Y. Jiang, H. Xu, and A. Ali Chandio. 2025. "Digital Inclusive Finance and Farmer Entrepreneurship: Pathways to Sustainable Development in Rural Ghana." *Sustainable Development* 34, no. 1: 65–79. <https://doi.org/10.1002/sd.70251>.
- Ahmad, S. 2025. "Information and Communication Technologies in Sustainable Crop Protection: Advancing Towards Sustainable Agriculture." *Proceedings of the Indian National Science Academy*: 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43538-025-00443-w>.
- Ajzen, I. 1991. "The Theory of Planned Behavior." *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes* 50, no. 2: 179–211. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0749-5978\(91\)90020-T](https://doi.org/10.1016/0749-5978(91)90020-T).
- Bahamonde-Birke, F. J., U. Kunert, H. Link, and J. D. D. Ortúzar. 2017. "About Attitudes and Perceptions: Finding the Proper Way to Consider Latent Variables in Discrete Choice Models." *Transportation* 44, no. 3: 475–493. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11116-015-9663-5>.
- Bahamonde-Birke, F. J., and J. D. D. Ortúzar. 2014. "On the Variability of Hybrid Discrete Choice Models." *Transportmetrica A: Transport Science* 10, no. 1: 74–88. <https://doi.org/10.1080/18128602.2012.700338>.
- Bandura, A. 1991. "Social Cognitive Theory of Self-Regulation." *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes* 50, no. 2: 248–287. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0749-5978\(91\)90022-L](https://doi.org/10.1016/0749-5978(91)90022-L).
- Bandura, A. 2006. "Guide for Constructing Self-Efficacy Scales." In *Self-Efficacy Beliefs of Adolescents*, vol. 5, 307–337. Emerald Publishing Limited.
- Barghusen, R., C. Sattler, L. Deijl, C. Weebers, and B. Matzdorf. 2021. "Motivations of Farmers to Participate in Collective Agri-Environmental Schemes: The Case of Dutch Agricultural Collectives." *Ecosystems and People* 17, no. 1: 539–555. <https://doi.org/10.1080/26395916.2021.1979098>.
- Bebber, D. P., T. Holmes, D. Smith, and S. J. Gurr. 2014. "Economic and Physical Determinants of the Global Distributions of Crop Pests and Pathogens." *New Phytologist* 202, no. 3: 901–910. <https://doi.org/10.1111/nph.12722>.
- Beedell, J., and T. Rehman. 2000. "Using Social-Psychology Models to Understand Farmers' Conservation Behaviour." *Journal of Rural Studies* 16, no. 1: 117–127. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0743-0167\(99\)00043-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0743-0167(99)00043-1).
- Ben-Akiva, M., D. McFadden, K. Train, et al. 2002. "Hybrid Choice Models: Progress and Challenges." *Marketing Letters* 13, no. 3: 163–175. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1020254301302>.
- Bjørnåvold, A., M. David, D. A. Bohan, C. Gibert, J.-M. Rousselle, and S. Van Passel. 2022. "Why Does France Not Meet Its Pesticide Reduction Targets? Farmers' Socio-Economic Trade-Offs When Adopting

- Agro-Ecological Practices." *Ecological Economics* 198: 107440. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2022.107440>.
- Bollen, K. A. 1989. *Structural Equations With Latent Variables*. 1st ed. Wiley. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118619179>.
- Boxall, P. C., and W. L. Adamowicz. 2002. "Understanding Heterogeneous Preferences in Random Utility Models: A Latent Cclass Approach." *Environmental and Resource Economics* 23, no. 4: 421–446. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1021351721619>.
- Broch, S. W., and S. E. Vedel. 2012. "Using Choice Experiments to Investigate the Policy Relevance of Heterogeneity in Farmer Agri-Environmental Contract Preferences." *Environmental and Resource Economics* 51, no. 4: 561–581. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10640-011-9512-8>.
- Byfuglien, A., A. M. Van Valkengoed, and S. Innocenti. 2025. "Good Intentions, Limited Action: When do Farmers' Intentions to Adopt Sustainable Farming Practices Turn Into Actual Behaviour?" *Journal of Environmental Psychology* 102: 102522. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvp.2025.102522>.
- Chang, S.-H.-E., E. O. Benjamin, and J. Sauer. 2024. "The Role of Rice Farmers' Attitude and Trust in Government in Decision-Making for Participating in a Climate-Related Agri-Environmental Scheme." *Journal of Environmental Planning and Management* 67, no. 8: 1724–1745. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09640568.2023.2180348>.
- Chèze, B., M. David, and V. Martinet. 2020. "Understanding Farmers' Reluctance to Reduce Pesticide Use: A Choice Experiment." *Ecological Economics* 167: 106349. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2019.06.004>.
- Chowdhury, A., and K. H. Kabir. 2024. "How Do Agricultural Advisory Services Meet the Needs of Farmers? Applying Q-Methodology to Assessing Multi-Stakeholders' Perspectives on the Pluralistic Advisory System in Ontario, Canada." *Journal of Rural Studies* 105: 103186. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrurstud.2023.103186>.
- Cialdini, R. B., R. R. Reno, and C. A. Kallgren. 1990. "A Focus Theory of Normative Conduct: Recycling the Concept of Norms to Reduce Littering in Public Places." *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology* 58, no. 6: 1015. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.58.6.1015>.
- Cole, L. J., D. Kleijn, L. V. Dicks, et al. 2020. "A Critical Analysis of the Potential for EU Common Agricultural Policy Measures to Support Wild Pollinators on Farmland." *Journal of Applied Ecology* 57, no. 4: 681–694. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2664.13572>.
- Courson, E., B. Ricci, L. Muneret, and S. Petit. 2024. "Reducing Pest Pressure and Insecticide Use by Increasing Hedgerows in the Landscape." *Science of the Total Environment* 916: 170182. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.170182>.
- Czajkowski, M., N. Hanley, and K. Nyborg. 2017. "Social Norms, Morals and Self-Interest as Determinants of Pro-Environment Behaviours: The Case of Household Recycling." *Environmental and Resource Economics* 66, no. 4: 647–670. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10640-015-9964-3>.
- Daly, A., S. Hess, B. Patrui, D. Potoglou, and C. Rohr. 2012. "Using Ordered Attitudinal Indicators in a Latent Variable Choice Model: A Study of the Impact of Security on Rail Travel Behaviour." *Transportation* 39, no. 2: 267–297. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11116-011-9351-z>.
- De Salvo, M., G. Cucuzza, S. L. Cosentino, L. Nicita, and G. Signorello. 2018. "Farmers' Preferences for Enhancing Sustainability in Arable Lands: Evidence From a Choice Experiment in Sicily (Italy)." *New Medit* 17, no. 4: 57–70. <https://doi.org/10.30682/nm1804e>.
- Deguine, J.-P., J.-N. Aubertot, R. J. Flor, F. Lescourret, K. A. G. Wyckhuys, and A. Ratnadass. 2021. "Integrated Pest Management: Good Intentions, Hard Realities. A Review." *Agronomy for Sustainable Development* 41, no. 3: 38. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13593-021-00689-w>.
- Despotović, J., V. Rodić, and F. Caracciolo. 2019. "Factors Affecting Farmers' Adoption of Integrated Pest Management in Serbia: An Application of the Theory of Planned Behavior." *Journal of Cleaner Production* 228: 1196–1205. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.04.149>.
- Dessart, F. J., J. Barreiro-Hurlé, and R. Van Bavel. 2019. "Behavioural Factors Affecting the Adoption of Sustainable Farming Practices: A Policy-Oriented Review." *European Review of Agricultural Economics* 46, no. 3: 417–471. <https://doi.org/10.1093/erae/jbz019>.
- Doherty, E., S. Mellett, D. Norton, T. K. J. McDermott, D. O. Hora, and M. Ryan. 2021. "A Discrete Choice Experiment Exploring Farmer Preferences for Insurance Against Extreme Weather Events." *Journal of Environmental Management* 290: 112607. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2021.112607>.
- Duesberg, S., D. O'Connor, and Á. N. Dhubbáin. 2013. "To Plant or Not to Plant—Irish Farmers' Goals and Values With Regard to Afforestation." *Land Use Policy* 32: 155–164. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2012.10.021>.
- Erekalo, K. T., M. Gemtou, M. Kornelis, S. M. Pedersen, T. Christensen, and S. Denver. 2025. "Understanding the Behavioral Factors Influencing Farmers' Future Adoption of Climate-Smart Agriculture: A Multi-Group Analysis." *Journal of Cleaner Production* 510: 145632. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2025.145632>.
- Feder, G., R. E. Just, and D. Zilberman. 1985. "Adoption of Agricultural Innovations in Developing Countries: A Survey." *Economic Development and Cultural Change* 33, no. 2: 255–298. <https://doi.org/10.1086/451461>.
- Finger, R. 2024. "Europe's Ambitious Pesticide Policy and Its Impact on Agriculture and Food Systems." *Agricultural Economics* 55, no. 2: 265–269. <https://doi.org/10.1111/agec.12817>.
- Finger, R., J. Sok, E. Ahovi, et al. 2024. "Towards Sustainable Crop Protection in Agriculture: A Framework for Research and Policy." *Agricultural Systems* 219: 104037. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agsy.2024.104037>.
- Fornell, C., and D. F. Larcker. 1981. "Evaluating Structural Equation Models With Unobservable Variables and Measurement Error." *Journal of Marketing Research* 18, no. 1: 39. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3151312>.
- Gao, Z., L. O. House, and X. Yu. 2010. "Using Choice Experiments to Estimate Consumer Valuation: The Role of Experimental Design and Attribute Information Loads." *Agricultural Economics* 41, no. 6: 555–565. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1574-0862.2010.00470.x>.
- Gasson, R. 1973. "Goals and Values of Farmers." *Journal of Agricultural Economics* 24, no. 3: 521–542. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1477-9552.1973.tb00952.x>.
- Gensch, L., K. Jantke, L. Rasche, and U. A. Schneider. 2024. "Pesticide Risk Assessment in European Agriculture: Distribution Patterns, Ban-Substitution Effects and Regulatory Implications." *Environmental Pollution* 348: 123836. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2024.123836>.
- Graskemper, V., X. Yu, and J.-H. Feil. 2022. "Values of Farmers – Evidence From Germany." *Journal of Rural Studies* 89: 13–24. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrurstud.2021.11.005>.
- Greene, W. H., and D. A. Hensher. 2003. "A Latent Class Model for Discrete Choice Analysis: Contrasts With Mixed Logit." *Transportation Research Part B: Methodological* 37, no. 8: 681–698. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0191-2615\(02\)00046-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0191-2615(02)00046-2).
- Hader, J. D., T. Lane, A. B. A. Boxall, M. MacLeod, and A. Di Guardo. 2022. "Enabling Forecasts of Environmental Exposure to Chemicals in European Agriculture Under Global Change." *Science of the Total Environment* 840: 156478. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.156478>.
- Han, G., and M. T. Niles. 2023. "An Adoption Spectrum for Sustainable Agriculture Practices: A New Framework Applied to Cover Crop Adoption." *Agricultural Systems* 212: 103771. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agsy.2023.103771>.

- Hedlund, J., S. B. Longo, and R. York. 2020. "Agriculture, Pesticide Use, and Economic Development: A Global Examination (1990–2014)." *Rural Sociology* 85, no. 2: 519–544. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ruso.12303>.
- Hess, S., and J. M. Rose. 2012. "Can Scale and Coefficient Heterogeneity Be Separated in Random Coefficients Models?" *Transportation* 39, no. 6: 1225–1239. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11116-012-9394-9>.
- Huber, J., and K. Zwerina. 1996. "The Importance of Utility Balance in Efficient Choice Designs." *Journal of Marketing Research* 33, no. 3: 307–317. <https://doi.org/10.1177/002224379603300305>.
- Hüttel, S., M.-T. Leuchten, and M. Leyer. 2022. "The Importance of Social Norm on Adopting Sustainable Digital Fertilisation Methods." *Organization & Environment* 35, no. 1: 79–102. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1086026620929074>.
- Joreskog, K. G., and A. S. Goldberger. 1975. "Estimation of a Model With Multiple Indicators and Multiple Causes of a Single Latent Variable." *Journal of the American Statistical Association* 70, no. 351: 631. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2285946>.
- Kaiser, A. 2023. "Discursive Struggles Over Pesticide Legitimacy in Switzerland: A News Media Analysis." *Environmental Innovation and Societal Transitions* 49: 100777. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eist.2023.100777>.
- Kaiser, A., R. Samuel, and P. Burger. 2024. "Toward a Low-Pesticide Agriculture: Bridging Practice Theory and Social-Psychological Concepts to Analyze Farmers' Routines." *Sustainability: Science, Practice and Policy* 20, no. 1: 2306731. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15487733.2024.2306731>.
- Kelemen, E., B. Megyesi, B. Matzdorf, et al. 2023. "The Prospects of Innovative Agri-Environmental Contracts in the European Policy Context: Results From a Delphi Study." *Land Use Policy* 131: 106706. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2023.106706>.
- Kim, J., S. Rasouli, and H. Timmermans. 2014. "Hybrid Choice Models: Principles and Recent Progress Incorporating Social Influence and Nonlinear Utility Functions." *Procedia Environmental Sciences* 22: 20–34. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.proenv.2014.11.003>.
- Knapp, L., D. Wuepper, and R. Finger. 2021. "Preferences, Personality, Aspirations, and Farmer Behavior." *Agricultural Economics* 52, no. 6: 901–913. <https://doi.org/10.1111/agec.12669>.
- Kreft, C., R. Huber, D. Wuepper, and R. Finger. 2021. "The Role of Non-Cognitive Skills in Farmers' Adoption of Climate Change Mitigation Measures." *Ecological Economics* 189: 107169. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2021.107169>.
- Kuhfeld, W. 2010. *Marketing Research Methods in SAS: Experimental Design, Choice, Conjoint, and Graphical Techniques*. Vol. 13. SAS Institute Inc.
- Larki Bolfarici, S., M. Zibaei, and D. Jahangirpour. 2024. "The Role of Market in Motivating Farmers to Reduce Pesticide Use: Evidence From Vegetable Farms in Shiraz." *Heliyon* 10, no. 15: e35055. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2024.e35055>.
- Le Coent, P., R. Préget, and S. Thoyer. 2021. "Farmers Follow the Herd: A Theoretical Model on Social Norms and Payments for Environmental Services." *Environmental and Resource Economics* 78, no. 2: 287–306. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10640-020-00532-y>.
- Leduc, G., L. Billaudet, E. Engström, H. Hansson, and M. Ryan. 2023. "Farmers' Perceived Values in Conventional and Organic Farming: A Comparison Between French, Irish and Swedish Farmers Using the Means-End Chain Approach." *Ecological Economics* 207: 107767. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2023.107767>.
- Leonnig, E. G., and J. Ø. Nielsen. 2026. "Knowledge and Innovation Exchanges in Organic Farmer Groups: Empirical Evidence From Germany." *Organic Agriculture* 16, no. 1: 4. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13165-025-00541-5>.
- Li, J., G. Liu, Y. Chen, and R. Li. 2023. "Study on the Influence Mechanism of Adoption of Smart Agriculture Technology Behavior." *Scientific Reports* 13, no. 1: 8554. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-35091-x>.
- Liu, H., and R. Brouwer. 2022. "Incentivizing the Future Adoption of Best Management Practices on Agricultural Land to Protect Water Resources: The Role of Past Participation and Experiences." *Ecological Economics* 196: 107389. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2022.107389>.
- Liu, M., and H. Liu. 2024. "Farmers' Adoption of Agriculture Green Production Technologies: Perceived Value or Policy-Driven?" *Heliyon* 10, no. 1: e23925. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e23925>.
- Luan, R., G. Wen, X. Hu, X. Lin, and C. Zhang. 2025. "Eco-Compensation for Farmers' Cultivated Land Protection Based on Field-Habitus Theory." *Ecological Indicators* 172: 113319. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2025.113319>.
- Lundhede, T., J. B. Jacobsen, N. Hanley, N. Strange, and B. J. Thorsen. 2015. "Incorporating Outcome Uncertainty and Prior Outcome Beliefs in Stated Preferences." *Land Economics* 91, no. 2: 296–316. <https://doi.org/10.3368/le.91.2.296>.
- Matousek, T., H. Mitter, B. Kropf, E. Schmid, and S. Vogel. 2022. "Farmers' Intended Weed Management After a Potential Glyphosate Ban in Austria." *Environmental Management* 69, no. 5: 871–886. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00267-022-01611-0>.
- Mausser, K. M., J. Wolfram, J. W. Spaak, C. Honert, and C. A. Brühl. 2025. "Current-Use Pesticides in Vegetation, Topsoil and Water Reveal Contaminated Landscapes of the Upper Rhine Valley, Germany." *Communications Earth & Environment* 6, no. 1: 166. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43247-025-02118-2>.
- McFadden, D. 1973. "Conditional Logit Analysis of Qualitative Choice Behaviour." In *P.Zeremba (Frontiers in Econometrics)*. Academic Press.
- Meunier, E., P. Smith, T. Griessinger, and C. Robert. 2024. "Understanding Changes in Reducing Pesticide Use by Farmers: Contribution of the Behavioural Sciences." *Agricultural Systems* 214: 103818. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agsy.2023.103818>.
- Miriti, P., and F. Lambarra-Lehnhardt. 2025. "Understanding Farmer Preferences and Trade-Offs for Adopting Sustainable Crop Production: A Systematic Review." *Discover Sustainability* 6, no. 1: 760. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43621-025-01591-1>.
- Miriti, P., F. Lambarra-Lehnhardt, X. Yu, S. Sieber, and R. Finger. 2025. "Reducing Pesticide Use: Insights Into Farmers' Preferences and Policy Implications for Integrated Pest Management Practices." <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.5195862>.
- Miriti, P., M. D. Regassa, C. O. Ojiewo, and M. B. Melesse. 2023. "Farmers' Preferences and Willingness to Pay for Traits of Sorghum Varieties: Informing Product Development and Breeding Programs in Tanzania." *Journal of Crop Improvement* 37, no. 2: 253–272. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15427528.2022.2079038>.
- Möhring, N., and R. Finger. 2022. "Pesticide-Free but Not Organic: Adoption of a Large-Scale Wheat Production Standard in Switzerland." *Food Policy* 106: 102188. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodpol.2021.102188>.
- Morugán-Coronado, A., M. D. Gómez-López, L. Meno, et al. 2024. "Fostering Sustainable Potato Production: A Collaborative European Approach." *Agronomy* 14, no. 12: 2762. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agronomy14122762>.
- Nagesh, P., O. Y. Edelenbosch, S. C. Dekker, H. J. De Boer, H. Mitter, and D. P. Van Vuuren. 2023. "Extending Shared Socio-Economic Pathways for Pesticide Use in Europe: Pest-Agri-SSPs." *Journal of Environmental Management* 342: 118078. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2023.118078>.
- Newman, A., M. Obschonka, S. Schwarz, M. Cohen, and I. Nielsen. 2019. "Entrepreneurial Self-Efficacy: A Systematic Review of the Literature on Its Theoretical Foundations, Measurement, Antecedents, and

- Outcomes, and an Agenda for Future Research." *Journal of Vocational Behavior* 110: 403–419. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvb.2018.05.012>.
- Oirdi, M. E., M. Yaseen, U. Farwa, et al. 2024. "Crops and People: The Dangers and Potential Benefits of Pesticides." *Cogent Food & Agriculture* 10, no. 1: 2334096. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311932.2024.2334096>.
- Oliveira, J. D. S. C., C. P. De Faria, and J. F. B. De São José. 2024. "Organic Food Consumers and Producers: Understanding Their Profiles, Perceptions, and Practices." *Heliyon* 10, no. 11: e31385. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2024.e31385>.
- Pannell, D. J., G. R. Marshall, N. Barr, A. Curtis, F. Vanclay, and R. Wilkinson. 2006. "Understanding and Promoting Adoption of Conservation Practices by Rural Landholders." *Australian Journal of Experimental Agriculture* 46, no. 11: 1407. <https://doi.org/10.1071/EA05037>.
- Raveau, S., R. Álvarez-Daziano, M. F. Yáñez, D. Bolduc, and J. De Dios Ortúzar. 2010. "Sequential and Simultaneous Estimation of Hybrid Discrete Choice Models: Some New Findings." *Transportation Research Record: Journal of the Transportation Research Board* 2156, no. 1: 131–139. <https://doi.org/10.3141/2156-15>.
- Regassa, M., G. Abate, and Z. Kubik. 2021. "Incentivising and Retaining Public Servants in Remote Areas: A Discrete Choice Experiment With Agricultural Extension Agents in Ethiopia." *Journal of Agricultural Economics* 72, no. 3: 878–900. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1477-9552.12432>.
- Regassa, M. D., P. Miriti, and M. B. Melesse. 2023. "Farmers' Heterogeneous Preferences for Traits of Improved Varieties: Informing Demand-Oriented Crop Breeding in Tanzania." *Experimental Agriculture* 59: e19. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0014479723000169>.
- Rogers, E. 2003. *Diffusion of Innovations*. (5th ed.). The Free Press.
- Rufo, E., R. Brouwer, and P. Van Beukering. 2024. "The Social Costs of Pesticides: A Meta-Analysis of the Experimental and Stated Preference Literature." *Scientific Reports* 14, no. 1: 31905. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-83298-3>.
- Sánchez Bogado, A. C., N. Estrada-Carmona, D. Beillouin, C. Chéron-Bessou, B. Rapidel, and S. K. Jones. 2024. "Farming for the Future: Understanding Factors Enabling the Adoption of Diversified Farming Systems." *Global Food Security* 43: 100820. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gfs.2024.100820>.
- Sarma, P. K. 2022. "Farmer Behavior Towards Pesticide Use for Reduction Production Risk: A Theory of Planned Behavior." *Cleaner and Circular Bioeconomy* 1: 100002. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clcb.2021.100002>.
- SAS Institute Inc. 2023. "JMP (Version 17) [Computer Software]." Cary, NC: SAS Institute 1989–2025 [17].
- Scarpa, R., R. Zanoli, V. Bruschi, and S. Naspetti. 2013. "Inferred and Stated Attribute Non-Attendance in Food Choice Experiments." *American Journal of Agricultural Economics* 95, no. 1: 165–180. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ajae/aas073>.
- Schermelleh-Engel, K., H. Moosbrugger, and H. Müller. 2003. "Evaluating the Fit of Structural Equation Models: Tests of Significance and Descriptive Goodness-of-Fit Measures." <https://doi.org/10.23668/PSYCHARCHIVES.12784>.
- Schneider, K., J. Barreiro-Hurle, and E. Rodriguez-Cerezo. 2023. "Pesticide Reduction Amidst Food and Feed Security Concerns in Europe." *Nature Food* 4, no. 9: 746–750. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43016-023-00834-6>.
- Schulze, C., K. Zagórska, K. Häfner, O. Markiewicz, M. Czajkowski, and B. Matzdorf. 2024. "Using Farmers' ex Ante Preferences to Design Agri-Environmental Contracts: A Systematic Review." *Journal of Agricultural Economics* 75, no. 1: 44–83. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1477-9552.12570>.
- Silva, V., X. Yang, L. Fleskens, C. J. Ritsema, and V. Geissen. 2022. "Environmental and Human Health at Risk – Scenarios to Achieve the Farm to Fork 50% Pesticide Reduction Goals." *Environment International* 165: 107296. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2022.107296>.
- Sok, J., I. van der Lans, H. Hogeveen, A. Elbers, and A. Lansink. 2018. "Farmers' Preferences for Bluetongue Vaccination Scheme Attributes: An Integrated Choice and Latent Variable Approach." *Journal of Agricultural Economics* 69, no. 2: 537–560. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1477-9552.12249>.
- Springmann, M., K. Wiebe, D. Mason-D'Croz, T. B. Sulser, M. Rayner, and P. Scarborough. 2018. "Health and Nutritional Aspects of Sustainable Diet Strategies and Their Association With Environmental Impacts: A Global Modelling Analysis With Country-Level Detail." *Lancet Planetary Health* 2, no. 10: e451–e461. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2542-5196\(18\)30206-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2542-5196(18)30206-7).
- Tama, R. A. Z., L. Ying, M. Yu, M. M. Hoque, K. M. Adnan, and S. A. Sarker. 2021. "Assessing Farmers' Intention Towards Conservation Agriculture by Using the Extended Theory of Planned Behavior." *Journal of Environmental Management* 280: 111654. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2020.111654>.
- Tourinho, P. S., Z. Hochmanová, P. Kukučka, et al. 2025. "Occurrence of Pesticide Residues in Harvested Products of Various Crops From European Conventional and Organic Farming Systems." *Journal of Hazardous Materials* 495: 139113. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2025.139113>.
- Tran, L., L. Mccann, and Y. Su. 2023. "Consumer Preferences for Produce Grown With Reduced Pesticides: A Choice Experiment in Missouri." *Renewable Agriculture and Food Systems* 38: e49. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1742170523000418>.
- Trèves, V., M. Hannachi, and J.-M. Meynard. 2025. "Enhancing Capacities for Sustainability Transition Policy Design: Lessons From French Pesticide Reduction Plans." *Agricultural Systems* 223: 104175. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agry.2024.104175>.
- Walker, J., and M. Ben-Akiva. 2002. "Generalized Random Utility Model." *Mathematical Social Sciences* 43, no. 3: 303–343. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0165-4896\(02\)00023-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0165-4896(02)00023-9).
- Wendt, M.-C., and R. Weinrich. 2023. "Consumer Segmentation for Pesticide-Free Food Products in Germany." *Sustainable Production and Consumption* 42: 309–321. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spc.2023.10.005>.
- Wuepper, D., S. Bukchin-Peles, D. Just, and D. Zilberman. 2023. "Behavioral Agricultural Economics." *Applied Economic Perspectives and Policy* 45, no. 4: 2094–2105. <https://doi.org/10.1002/aep.13343>.
- Wyckhuys, K. A. G., Y. Zou, T. C. Wanger, W. Zhou, Y. D. Gc, and Y. Lu. 2022. "Agro-Ecology Science Relates to Economic Development but Not Global Pesticide Pollution." *Journal of Environmental Management* 307: 114529. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2022.114529>.
- Zemo, K. H., and M. Termansen. 2022. "Environmental Identity Economics: An Application to Farmers' Pro-Environmental Investment Behaviour." *European Review of Agricultural Economics* 49, no. 2: 331–358. <https://doi.org/10.1093/erae/jbab049>.

Appendix A

TABLE A1 | Measures to prevent, monitor and combat diseases, pests and weeds by Polish potato farmers.

IPM practices	Class 1 (%)	Class 2 (%)
Use of adjuvants	15.56	18.29
Use of beneficial organisms (e.g., ladybugs, lacewings, hoverflies, aphids)	16.67	13.41
Shaping the architecture of the field (i.e., larger spacing between rows and plants in rows)	11.11	17.07
Sprout seed potatoes	22.22	17.07
Site-specific crop rotation	45.56	53.66
Adjustment of seed density	45.56	60.98
Creating and promoting ecological habitats (e.g., flower strips, hedges or wildflowers to encourage beneficial insects)	22.22	21.95
Field hygiene (e.g., keeping manure (or compost) free of weed seeds, using certified potato seed)	70.00	68.29
Intensive mechanical weed control (e.g., working the soil with a plough and cultivator/harrow/mill)	41.11	36.59
Regular monitoring of pest and weed infestation (e.g., by visual inspections, traps or nets)	25.56	32.93
Low to medium mechanical weed control (e.g., working the soil without a plough and instead with a cultivator/harrow/mill)	38.89	48.78
Direct sowing	16.67	12.20
Selection of varieties with high resistance (e.g., varieties that are resistant to fungi/insects/other pests)	41.11	46.34
Adjustment of the sowing time	52.22	62.20
Orientation toward official damage thresholds	24.44	23.17
Use of forecasting and warning systems for pests and diseases (e.g., from plant protection services)	24.44	30.49

Note: The table presents the percentage of farmers in each latent class who reported using various IPM practices.

TABLE A2 | Measures to prevent, monitor and combat diseases, pests and weeds by German potato farmers.

IPM practices	Class 1 (%)	Class 2 (%)
Use follow-up crops	40.60	46.67
Use of glyphosate to control weeds and cover crops during no-till establishment	37.33	33.33
Use of forecast models (e.g., SIMBLIGHT/SIMPHYT)	24.67	16.67
Selection of varieties with high resistance (e.g., varieties that are resistant to fungi/insects/other pests)	46.00	60.00
Site-specific crop rotation	62.67	56.67
Adjustment of seed density	50.67	43.33
Creating and promoting ecological habitats (e.g., flower strips, hedges or wildflowers to encourage beneficial insects)	57.33	63.33
Green manuring	39.33	46.67
Field hygiene (e.g., keeping manure (or compost) free of weed seeds, using certified potato seed)	72.00	76.67
Regular monitoring of pest and weed infestation (e.g., by visual inspections, traps or nets)	46.00	60.00
Adjustment of the sowing time	57.33	33.33
Orientation toward official damage thresholds	39.33	30.00
Use of forecasting and warning systems for pests and diseases (e.g., from plant protection services)	50.67	40.00

Note: The table presents the percentage of farmers in each latent class who reported using various IPM practices.

TABLE A3 | Attributes and levels.

Attributes	Description	Levels
Source of Integrated Pest Management advisory support	The source from which advisory support is received	No support, public bodies, private bodies
Reduction of pesticide residues	Reduction of pesticide residues in the environment, especially in water bodies and soil	Small, substantial
Time to start/transition to implementing Integrated Pest Management practices	In how many years from now is the farmer supposed to implement integrated pest management practices	In 2 years, in 4 years, in 6 years
Farm income	The average changes in farm income per hectare in a year	5% decrease, no change, 5% increase
Production reduction in a cropping season	The average expected production losses in a cropping season	Production reduces by 5%, production reduces by 10%, production reduces by 15%

Note: Attributes and levels are designed to capture tradeoffs and variations in economic, environmental, and temporal dimensions of IPM, ensuring the relevance and credibility of the discrete choice experiment.

TABLE A4 | The ICLV model with one latent variable.

Mean estimates of variables	Coefficients	Std error	p
Farm income	0.106	0.011	0.000
IPM advisory support (reference: no support)			
Private	0.170	0.108	0.116
Public	0.255	0.100	0.011
Reduction of pesticide residues (reference: small)			
Substantial	0.009	0.086	0.919
Transition time to full IPM (reference: 2 years)			
4 years	0.041	0.096	0.670
6 years	-0.009	0.109	0.936
Production losses in a cropping season (reference: production reduces by 15%)			
Production reduces by 5%	0.244	0.106	0.021
Production reduces by 10%	0.042	0.102	0.677
Self-efficacy	0.079	0.035	0.022
Measurement model			
[...] problem in potato production, I usually find a solution [...]	0.828	0.053	0.000
[...] solve most problems in crop protection [...]	0.669	0.048	0.000
[...] reduce pesticides and at the same time produce [...]	2.941	0.372	0.000
Structural component			
Age of the farmer	0.242	0.028	0.000
Higher education (1 yes; 0 otherwise)	0.004	0.058	0.945
Planned farm succession	0.593	0.064	0.000

(Continues)

TABLE A4 | (Continued)

Mean estimates of variables	Coefficients	Std error	p
Organic production	1.153	0.071	0.000
Crop yield insurance	0.332	0.057	0.000
Crop protection information from:			
Other farmers	-0.079	0.055	0.149
Farmers' organization	0.204	0.062	0.001
Plant protection product manufacturers	0.142	0.053	0.007
Number of respondents	180		
Number of observations	2160		
Log-likelihood	-13582.646		

Note: The model is estimated using a simultaneous ICLV approach incorporating one latent variable. The model reveals that German potato farmers have a positive preference for IPM practices that are likely to increase farm income, shorter transition time, and substantial pesticide residue reduction. Farmers' self-efficacy positively influences IPM choices, suggesting self-efficacy promotes the uptake of IPM. The measurement model further highlights the significant associations between self-efficacy and farmer characteristics.

TABLE A5 | Simulated maximum likelihood (ML) estimates from the mixed logit model.

Mean estimates of variables	Poland			Germany				
	Structural preference parameters	SD of the parameter distributions		Structural preference parameters		SD of the parameter distributions		
	Coeff	SE	Coeff	SE	Coeff	SE	Coeff	SE
Farm income	0.071***	0.022	0.193***	0.034	0.100***	0.017	0.130***	0.024
IPM advisory support (reference: no support)								
Private	0.681***	0.168	0.894***	0.300	0.312***	0.113	0.163	0.517
Public	0.486***	0.134	0.673***	0.256	0.272***	0.099	0.186	0.405
Reduction of pesticide residues (reference: small)								
Substantial	0.025	0.115	0.553**	0.235	0.074	0.091	0.474***	0.171
Transition time (reference: 2years)								
4 years	0.090	0.126	0.350	0.289	0.188*	0.101	0.145	0.397
6 years	0.060	0.166	0.714**	0.293	0.155	0.113	0.014	0.259
Production losses in a cropping season (reference: production reduces by 15%)								
Production reduces by 5%	0.562***	0.163	0.979***	0.250	0.379***	0.108	0.047	0.185
Production reduces by 10%	0.151	0.131	-0.205	0.346	0.243**	0.110	0.161	0.371
Number of respondents	172				180			
Number of observations	2064				2160			
Log-likelihood	-656.691				-691.011			

Note: The results reveal several statistically significant factors shaping farmers' preference for IPM in both Poland and Germany. In both countries, farmers are more likely to adopt IPM practices that increase farm income. Farmers prefer advisory support from public and private sources; however, farmers in both countries express a greater preference for private advisory services. In Germany, a substantial reduction in pesticide residues significantly influences preferences, suggesting a stronger concern for environmental outcomes compared to Polish farmers. Additionally, both Polish and German farmers prefer IPM options associated with lower production losses, especially where only a 5% reduction in yield is expected. ***, ** and * denote statistical significance at the 1%, 5% levels and 10% respectively.

TABLE A6 | Model fit statistics for latent class model.

Country	Classes	LLF	Nparam	AIC	BIC
Poland	2	-665.315	16	1428.990	1412.990
	3	-654.239	24	1456.018	1432.018
	4	-650.178	32	1497.076	1465.076
Germany	2	-679.429	16	1457.945	1441.945
	3	-671.739	24	1492.109	1468.109
	4	-658.25	32	1514.674	1482.674

Note: A model with two classes has the lowest AIC and BIC values for both Germany and Poland; therefore, a model with two classes was estimated.

Attribute	Option A	Option B
Source of Integrated Pest Management (IPM) advisory support	No support 	
Reduction of pesticide residues	Small 	
Time to start implementing Integrated Pest Management (IPM) practices	In 4 years 	
Farm income	No change 	
Production losses	Production reduces by 5% 	

FIGURE A1 | Example of a choice card.